

Diseases of Melons: Reasons, Symptoms, and Methods of Control

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ABSTRACT: The article provides information about the main diseases of melons and control measures. Melons diseases and pests will not damage the quality or quantity of the crop if you understand their fundamental characteristics, preventative techniques, and treatment options. And the issue of why they become yellow, why seedling leaves twist, why worms arise in melons, and why stems rust will no longer be a dead end after reading the essay. Another fungal disease that affects medium and late-ripening melons is Fusarium wilt. It can appear when the seedlings of anything have 2-3 genuine leaves or when the fruit is about to mature. Melon leaves wilt, turn yellow, and become rusty gray.

KEY WORDS: melon, symptom, diseases, method, control, active

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INTRODUCTION

Many melons, particularly melons, have a tendency to become infected with numerous illnesses. Melon illnesses are classified by pathogen type: viruses, bacteria, and fungus. And it is not only the fate of professionals in microbiological laboratories but also of regular gardeners, to understand the differences between different sorts of illnesses. Fighting them will be less expensive after you learn to make an accurate diagnosis and administer the appropriate and effective therapy. Melons diseases and pests will not damage the quality or quantity of the crop if you understand their fundamental characteristics, preventative techniques, and treatment options. And the issue of why they become yellow, why seedling leaves twist, why worms arise in melons, and why stems rust will no longer be a dead end after reading the essay.

Peronosporosis (false powdery mildew) is a fungus-caused disease that causes yellow-green patches on melon leaves. Spotting and rust appear during the early stages of plant growth and spread quickly. Later, a gray plaque forms on the melon's leaves, indicating that the fungus is sporulating.

Downy mildew may be prevented by heating the seeds in a thermos for 2 hours at 45 degrees and then dipping them in a 1 percent manganese solution for 20 minutes. If the illness has not yet taken hold of the plant and the leaves are fast yellowing, apply a urea and Bordeaux combination solution. Then you can use pharmaceuticals like "Topaz" and "oksihom," as long as you follow the dose instructions on the packaging. This is the most frequent watermelon illness, and you only need to be aware of the symptoms. It's time to raise the alarm if little white spots form on the stems and leaves of melons. Powdery mildew in its active period should not be allowed to twist, dry, or even turn dark brown the leaves.

1. Picture (False powdery mildew)

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Another fungal disease that affects medium and late-ripening melons is Fusarium wilt. It can appear when the seedlings of anything have 2-3 genuine leaves or when the fruit is about to mature. Melon leaves wilt, turn yellow, and become rusty gray. The plant might die totally in a week, and if the melon is saved using pesticides, the fruits will no longer be as delicious and juicy, and the yield will be cut in half.

Crop rotation is the greatest way to avoid powdery mildew, just as it is with powdery mildew. Wilting is inevitable when melons are planted in lieu of their near relatives because fungal infections grow in the soil. If the symptoms of fusarium will persist, replenish with phosphate or potassium.

Anthracnose, sometimes known as "copper," is a kind of anthracnose. Yellow or pink-brown rusty patches cover the leaves, which become brittle and dry as a result of this illness. Fruits get misshapen and decay as well. Anthracnose may be avoided by removing any plant material from the landing location. Bordeaux fluid and sulfur solution are used to cure anthracnose. At the first symptom of the sickness, precautions should be taken.

2. Picture (*Fusarium wilt*)

Affects the plants that are the most vulnerable. Rust coats their roots and stems, turning them brown. The cotyledons and leaves then dry up, and the plant dies. Before planting, disinfect the seeds in formalin to protect the melon from root rot. Bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas syringae*, class actinomycete, cause the illness. Furthermore, a temperature of over 25 ° C, as well as humidity, are advantageous to the disease's progression. Bacteria are spread by the wind, insects, and water.

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